

Recommended citation: Eckert, N., Gallenkämper, J., Heiß, H., Kreulich, K., Mooraj, M., Müller, C., Müller, G., Schumann, C., Sowa, T., & Spiegelberg, G. (2018). Engineering Education for the Digital Transformation. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 780-798). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672699.

SMART GERMANY

ENGINEERING EDUCATION FOR THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Discussion paper for the
VDI Quality Dialogue

VDI theses and
fields of action
March 2018

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We would like to thank our discussion partners:

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Summary

The Digital Transformation is currently permeating all fields of engineering with an intensity hitherto unknown. The following theses describe the current situation as perceived by the authors. The consequences for engineer training have been extrapolated from this and impulses for curriculum development have been derived.

Part 1: Theses regarding Digital Transformation

Society, personal life, professional world, and world of work

Digital Transformation will change the world of work fundamentally.

The key enabler is imparting the necessary skills for accessing digitized areas of life.

Social competences for an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration provide a decisive additional benefit for value creation and research. Engineers bear the ethical responsibility for what they create.

Education for the Digital Transformation

Digital Transformation needs to become part of the curriculum.

Sensitizing with regard to social acceptance and change forms a part of an education for the Digital Transformation.

Digital Transformation makes new forms of teaching and learning possible.

Digitized teaching will occupy a growing share of educational processes.

Globalized and lifelong digital learning

Open education – education for all – will be facilitated by the Digital Transformation.

Digital Transformation is leading to a stronger individualization of educational and life planning. All interfaces of education and continuing education are to be mutually coordinated in the process of lifelong learning.

The selection and evaluation of information is becoming more important, while the relevance of easily accessible knowledge is declining.

Part 2: Consequences for engineering education

The natural way digital natives handle digital means of communication does not yet imply any deeper understanding of the Digital Transformation. In addition to the classical content of an engineering study program, skills in this area are essential. This not only includes the technological content but also the understanding of new business models, data security and protection, as well as social implications.

Since Digital Transformation acts at the interfaces of current domains, an extensive competence in collaboration going beyond the ability to work in a team is necessary. Here, regularly scheduled collaborations should take place even during the degree course, not only campus-wide but also reaching out externally as well.

Knowledge globally available on the internet ensures that the importance of self-learning competence is constantly growing.

Part 3: Impulses for curriculum development

Digital Transformation affects the entire course of studies. For each module the questions must be asked as to how and to what extent Digital Transformation requires a change in the skills profile of the participants. Digital Transformation must be incorporated integrally and not simply pasted on.

New content for the engineering course is sorted into various levels of abstraction (model level, system level, technology level and application level). To do so, a third dimension representing the degree of digitization is added to the commonly used T-shape model.

The authors take the view that easily accessible knowledge should give way to new content if it is not fundamentally important. Competence in selecting and assessing information on the internet is increasing in importance.

The social responsibility of engineers is changing with the digitization of engineering products and is receiving new challenges. This must be reflected in the course of studies. Students need the ability to assess the impact of technology and to act according to their judgment.

To support curriculum development, a dialogue process with external partners is presented. Through a dialog between the institutes of higher education and partners from business, a critical light should be thrown on the course content and the expected skills of graduates.

Educational requirements and prospects for engineering in Digital Transformation

The Digital Transformation is currently permeating all fields of engineering with an intensity hitherto unknown. Institutes of higher education should not only respond to this but also contribute to this radical change. In order for the engineers of tomorrow to be well prepared for the digital world of work and research, it is necessary for the Digital Transformation to be fundamentally reflected in the upcoming further developments of the curricula.

Curriculum development is a process that must be carried out regularly. It is imperative that it takes the Digital Transformation into account. This discussion paper is to be understood as a basis for discussion with experts from the institutes of higher education, business and politics. Present needs are here delineated from the current point of view of the authors. It does not represent a positioning of the VDI.

This discussion paper is divided into three sections. First of all, an approach is made to the change in education on an abstract level in the form of theses, which were initiated by the VDI's Interdisciplinary Committee on Digital Transformation. In a second step, the consequences for engineering education are extrapolated. The focus here is on Digital Transformation as a teaching content in contrast to digitized teaching, since the use of digital media for new teaching formats and didactic variants is already very advanced locally and is in development throughout

Germany, whereas revision of the curricula in terms of Digital Transformation is frequently in the early stages in classical engineering courses.

The third part then deals with impulses for the development process for engineering course curricula as part of Digital Transformation. Here, the approach of an integrated incorporation into the study programs is pursued rather than an additive one. This part should in particular be seen as a proposal for a systematic exchange between institutes of higher education and companies.

Since 2007, the VDI Quality Dialogue on higher education has provided a prominent forum that facilitates discussions between representatives from the institutes of higher education, politics and industry, as well as demonstrating good practice examples. The authors welcome the fact that the value of engineering education has increased in recent years and they will also continue to support this.

The 6th VDI Quality Dialogue, which will be held on 1st and 2nd March 2018 at the TU Berlin¹, will focus on the second and third parts of this discussion paper, facilitate an intensive exchange between the institutes of higher education and companies, and provide a platform for good practice examples.

Düsseldorf, February 2018

¹ www.vdi.de/bildung/qualitaetsdialoge

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Part 1: Theses on Digital Transformation

Higher education is always guided by the current state of knowledge and by the present and future challenges that professionals and leaders face. Technological innovations are taken up in the context of the cyclical revision of courses and anchored in the curricula. The ever-accelerating advancement of digital technologies more than ever requires a renewal of qualification goals and educational content.

Digital Transformation stands for the global change in the economy and in society, caused by the systematic penetration of daily life by information and communication technologies (ICT). This change has an impact on all areas of life and encompasses all sectors of industry. It interacts closely with the way we live, operate economically and work.

The obvious progress in key scientific fields such as data science/data engineering, artificial intelligence and digital networking not only stands for a further development and improvement of what already exists but also gives rise to a variety of replacements for existing applications. Physical systems and processes are constantly being digitized. This leads to optimizations of existing as well as to the emergence of entirely new concepts and applications, which are only possible through the use of digital technologies. Data and algorithms are available for the evaluation of any interaction and complex processes. Robots and autonomous systems can solve problems without human intervention. In the internet of things, information is exchanged instantaneously between people, machines and arbitrary things. This goes hand in hand with a great responsibility on the part of the individuals involved – in particular, the engineers. They must get involved creatively in a normative environment, even in social discourse.

Institutes of higher education must prepare their future graduates for Digital Transformation. The following theses are based on the current perception of the authors and list the associated challenges.

1 Society, personal life, the professional world, and the world of work

Digital Transformation permeates all areas of society and affects all developmental, transformational and

application processes even in education. Education has a multivalent task both as an application field as well as a mediator and thus also as a driver of the Digital Transformation. The goal must be a digitally mature and enlightened society.

1.1 Digital Transformation will change the world of work fundamentally

Work will be digitized and automated, which causes a **high qualification pressure** for the general public and, above all, for those working in the STEM sector, who are the drivers and shapers of Digital Transformation. The digitization of jobs creates a clear change in professional requirements and leads to **new job profiles and occupational profiles with different skills shapes** in new work environments.

1.2 The key enabler is imparting the necessary skills for accessing digitized areas of life

The basic requirement for the participation of wider layers of society in future living, learning and working environments is **imparting the necessary skills** for dealing with digitized areas of life. First of all, the access threshold to digital systems and components must be surmountable in order to be able to participate and share in the development and utilization of digital worlds. **Access will be on diversified levels**, where the degree of subjective skill-building will decide on the form and extent of participation and sharing in digital processes.

1.3 Social competences for an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration provide a decisive additional benefit for value creation and research

Digital Transformation succeeds through an **interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration**. In order to work with the perspective of other disciplines, strengthening of the necessary social skills is required. This should be understood as a **decisive added value**.

1.4 Engineers bear the ethical responsibility for what they create

Technologies deeply affect people's lives and work as well as the natural world. **Regardless of digitization**, engineers must even today bear the **ethical responsibility** for what they have created. However, **with digitization new dimensions** are added in the necessary **technology assessment**.

2 Education for the Digital Transformation

From the author's perspective, teaching and learning in the context of Digital Transformation includes two main aspects. For one thing, teaching itself is digitized, being often referred to as e-learning or already as digital education. Digitized teaching is, for example, the use of digital teaching and learning platforms or the use of digital tools in the classical lecture. On the other hand, however, Digital Transformation must itself become a subject of teaching, as has already been shown. Both aspects of digital education need to be implemented in order to educate people for Digital Transformation.

Even if the development of curricula with regard to Digital Transformation stands at the forefront of the VDI Quality Dialogue and this discussion paper, the digitization of teaching and Digital Transformation as a learning content cannot always be sharply separated from each other. In order to impart the new teaching content effectively and sustainably, the use of digitized teaching methods is often necessary, but is at least useful.

2.1 Digital Transformation needs to become part of the curriculum.

Comprehensive teaching of the necessary skills for Digital Transformation requires an **uncomplicated handling of digitized teaching** because without a hands-on approach to digital media and methods, many fundamental systematics of digitization cannot be conceived. More important, however, is the **imparting of skills for the Digital Transformation** as such and its critical examination.

2.2 Sensitizing with regard to social acceptance and change forms a part of an education for the Digital Transformation.

Part of an education for the Digital Transformation is **raising awareness with regard to social acceptance and change**, which itself changes due to intrinsically intelligent autonomous systems as technology and their daily use. The goal should be to **create a sense of responsibility and an interface competence** as a basis for shaping the social transformation processes triggered by technological progress.

2.3 Digital Transformation makes new forms of teaching and learning possible

Digital Transformation makes **new forms of teaching and learning** possible and creates new space for both cooperative and also individualized learning. The didactic and content-related limits of existing forms of teaching can be expanded and new worlds of learning opened up - especially in the context of not only stronger networking but also digital platforms and tools. This is accompanied by **greater efficiency and effectiveness for learners and teachers**. The merging of real and virtual learning environments, the interplay of knowledge acquisition and application, ratiocination, and also many other forms of skills training can be redesigned.

2.4 Digitized teaching will occupy a growing share of educational processes

Digitized teaching will occupy a growing share of educational processes and thereby enter into a symbiosis with existing educational formats. Digitization of education will in particular take place in those areas in which it can significantly contribute to the **improvement of teaching and learning processes** and of knowledge transformations. Part of this development is the spread of digital formats such as massive open online courses or digital learning management in the field of education. Moreover, **digital business models outside of traditional education providers** are pressing into the education market.

3 Globalized and lifelong digitized learning

In all areas of working life, Digital Transformation is creating new requirements for lifelong learning. But even in private everyday life, Digital Transformation has a considerable influence. Aspects such as the barrier-free accessibility of new applications play an important role in participation in social life, which increasingly requires an uncomplicated dealing with new technologies.

Digital Transformation opens up new possibilities in the context of globalization. In the educational context, Digital Transformation can weaken regional differences and create an access to education which is independent of location.

The digitization of knowledge and of teaching enables completely new dimensions for a use by broad strata of society. Both the social dialogue about technology-driven developments and also education and further education can thus be designed sustainably and economically.

3.1 Open education – education for all – is facilitated by the Digital Transformation

Education for all – worldwide access to data, information and knowledge – is only possible on a wide scale through the digitization of education. Open education not only includes changes in the global use of knowledge but must also promote **intergenerational learning, both regionally and globally.**

3.2 Digital Transformation is leading to a stronger individualization of educational and life planning

Digitized education processes promote interlinking of education and further education as well as **individualization of educational and life planning.** Opportunities arise not only for individual ways of acquiring skills together with a higher permeability in the education system but also for individual skills profiles for each person, especially through further education.

3.3 All interfaces of education and continuing education are to be mutually coordinated in the process of lifelong learning

All interfaces of education and continuing education in the digital world of education should be mutually **coordinated in the process of lifelong learning, from the kindergarten up to senior citizens' academies,** in order to support learners with a sustainable social participation and with uninterrupted personal and vocational development.

3.4 The selection and evaluation of information is becoming more important, while the relevance of easily accessible knowledge is declining

Digital Transformation promotes networking in the field of education. The widespread availability of global knowledge enables the easy integration of many sources of information. Connectivistic learning and the selection of important information thus gains a growing significance. The relevance of providing easily accessible knowledge is decreasing.

Part 2: Consequences for engineering education

Engineers play a central role in the Digital Transformation since they are significant drivers of digital change. An engineering course must impart in an appropriate way the skills needed for Digital Transformation so that for research and for business young talent is qualified for the future.

In a disruptive process such as the Digital Transformation all stakeholders involved in engineering education need to rethink their structures and processes. In this part of the discussion paper, the authors will extrapolate the consequences for the content-related design of engineering education on the basis of the theses in the first part. In doing so, the theses relating to course content will be treated more intensively. The other theses in the first part cover the context of the overall situation, as the authors currently perceive it, but here are relegated to the margins. For example, no extra-curricular possibilities, such as in-company training or non-university online courses, are considered. It is further assumed that educational qualifications appropriate to higher education entrance have been obtained before taking up studies.

Digital Transformation is an integral process that affects all areas of the engineering sciences, and each module of a course of study. Even if a specially created (preferably interdisciplinary) module during the course of studies can shed light on the general facets of the Digital Transformation, nevertheless, each individual module should in its own context be examined and further developed in terms of the effects of the Digital Transformation. The intensity should be graduated according to its relevance within the modules. As described in the first part, a fundamental change in society goes hand in hand with Digital Transformation. The technical solutions of today and tomorrow have a much more direct influence than was still the case 20 years ago. Thus, the social responsibility increases. Different aspects of curriculum development are highlighted in what follows.

Skills prior to entry upon studies

Younger generations who have grown up with digital communications technology in their everyday life – so-called digital natives – have already been markedly influenced by the Digital Transformation. Today they **can as a rule use digital formats**

and communication processes in a much more straightforward way than many lecturers. In order to optimize and professionalize their teaching, teachers should be familiar with the methods of **digitally supported teaching and use them purposefully** (↗ Thesis 2.3). In the institutes of higher education there should be central support offices to help lecturers in the **conversion of didactics**.

The fact that today's students are absolutely at home in their dealings with certain digital media **does not mean that they also have an in-depth understanding of the technologies** (↗ Thesis 2.1) nor of the possibilities and limits of Digital Transformation and its **impact on society and the environment** (↗ Thesis 2.2).

Personal and social skills

Existing knowledge is increasing rapidly in both its extent and its depth of detail. To be sure of finding and appraising the necessary information in any situation, **self-learning competence** (↗ Thesis 3.4) must be included as a learning objective in new and existing curricula.

Still important characteristics are decision-making ability and cooperation skills.

The decision-making ability (↗ Theses 3.2 and 3.4) is the ability to focus on what is essential, to set priorities and to assess alternatives in order to act and to rely on one's experience in unpredictable situations. The more possibilities there are, the more important this skill is. Digital Transformation is contributing to a massive increase in opportunities in many areas.

Cooperation competence (↗ Thesis 1.3) is the ability to collaborate in social, technical and business matters, to achieve consensus and mutual acceptance. In addition to team ability it also includes the ability to enter into partnerships outside the organization. This includes the active implementation of a constructive feedback culture. It is important on the one hand to promote mutual acceptance on the part of the students and, on the other hand, to utilize the increased possibilities of individualized feedback and thus provide transparency.²

² Based on Erpenbeck, J.; Heyse V.: Die Kompetenzbiografie. Waxmann 2007

In order to convey **appreciative and goal-oriented cooperation behaviour** to students, corresponding learning objectives should be integrated into the curricula and explicitly promoted in teaching through feedback and the creation of reflection events.

Technical skills and the imparting of knowledge

In the third part of this discussion paper, a portfolio of specific technical skills is listed. The authors will therefore confine themselves at this point to general statements about professional skills and knowledge dissemination.

In the future there will be a **greater need for graduates with hybrid skills**; in other words, domain know-how in an engineering discipline paired with solid basic knowledge in digital disciplines (↗ Thesis 1.1). Conversely, computer scientists are sought who bring a basic understanding into the context of the classic engineering sciences. With the aid of interdisciplinary modules, which operate, for example, **by using problem-based learning methods, students from various disciplines can learn from each other and at the same time strengthen their interdisciplinary skills** (↗ Thesis 1.3).

New educational content for Digital Transformation should not be a pure mediation of information about it, but must rather **strengthen the ability to transfer information by combination into new knowledge and knowledge into new conclusions** (↗ Thesis 3.4).

Therefore, there must be a focus on such teaching content as conveys combination, abstraction, modelling, knowledge about model boundaries, risk assessment and containment, interfacing skills with other disciplines, documentation and communication of data and results, data analysis and quality assurance of the knowledge constantly available on the internet. This will only work under a challenging re-adjustment of the teaching content with a **reduction in the easily accessible knowledge**.

In addition, the **special relevance of the options in the digital world should be communicated – especially through the now widespread connection to the internet**. Digital mappings of real objects and processes have long been part of the simulation methods routinely used by engineers. What is new, however, is the comprehensive networking of real and virtual information so that entire ecosystems can be mapped as digital twins and the communication and development possibilities of the individuals involved

can be raised to a different level. Not only in this way are predictive simulations made possible which then, following activation of the derived, simulated measures, have a direct impact on the real-life models or their modification by computational steering and artificial intelligence. The **digital world is increasingly controlling the real world**; this calls for an appropriate awareness in this way of thinking.

The development of products and entire scenarios in the virtual world requires a deep understanding of the underlying models and their limits, of the **simulation technologies** (↗ Thesis 2.1), their tools and process chains. Furthermore, essential business models are organized in the digital world which are then however implemented in the real world via the acquisition of information using sensors and execution by actuators (such as machines in manufacturing, autonomous vehicles in the context of mobility). The creation of **control loops between the virtual and the real world** is significantly intensifying; for this reason, a broad understanding of the possibilities of these two worlds should be imparted. Here, the simulation of real processes and the intelligent filtering of large amounts of data is also just as much a key skill as is knowledge of agile process methods in software development.

Ethics and society

Engineers should perform their actions with an **ethical and professional responsibility** (↗ Thesis 1.4) towards society and the environment. The prerequisite for this is an ethical discourse in engineering education: not only topics such as data protection and misuse as well as data security and data falsification, but also the decision-making parameters of autonomous systems are part of engineering products. There is a need for competence in **technology assessment**.

Digitization is speeding up global networking, which in particular enables a global exchange of information in which many people participate. In the education of future engineers, **space should be made to allow for reflection about cultural constraints or changes in their effect on technical fields of work** (↗ Thesis 1.2).

Part of digital education is to develop a sense of responsibility and an **interface competence** as the basis for the design of social transformation processes triggered by technological advances (↗ Thesis 2.2).

Engineers must participate actively in critical reflection and in the social impact assessment of new technologies and share a formative role in normative processes. They must bring their expertise to

the forefront of societal discourse so that regulatory frameworks can be adjusted to promote progress and competitiveness and to enable the implementation of innovative solutions. In this way they can contribute to **shaping the discourse objectively on a scientific basis**.

Engineers have also the responsibility of contributing to solutions for the regulation and control of uncontrolled developments resulting from digitization in different areas. **Misuse of digital technologies** is not only harmful to consumers, the environment or the economy, but also to the reputation of engineering as a whole and must be prevented at all costs.

Students must be put into a position of **independently subjecting their actions to ethical examination**, coming to their own judgments, and acting in accordance with ethically-based criteria (↗ Thesis 1.4).

Understanding of quality and safety

Even the **understanding of quality and the quality requirements of engineering products** must take account of Digital Transformation (↗ Thesis 2.1). It is generally known that software solutions can never be a hundred percent safe. This does, however, mean that students need to develop an understanding of the right level of safety measures and the limits of the underlying model approaches. For example, in connection with products in the area of the 'Internet of Things' (IoT), an awareness of the different speeds of the product development cycles of all product components is essential. For instance, while the refrigeration technology of a refrigerator is designed to last 20 to 30 years, the software is already a security risk after a relatively short time. This must already be taken into consideration in development.

Furthermore, **data protection and data security** are unavoidably the responsibility of engineers.

It is well known that products can be made mechanically much simpler and more unstable if they can be electronically stabilized by digital measures such as control technology (for example, ESP in the car). Here, current Digital Transformation is yielding increasingly wide-ranging opportunities for developing **modified quality requirements on a mechanical basis with higher quality on the overall system level**. The focus must always be on the latter.

In principle, an increased importance is given to **weighing up the advantages of quality assurance before and after completion of a product**. In this

regard, it is a matter of determining which areas need to be differentiated right from the start and which can, via updates based on user data, lead to a significant added value during the lifetime of the product. This increased number of degrees of freedom should be reflected in the course of studies.

Forms of organization

The questions to be tackled in the digital world of work and life are steadily becoming more and more complex. New digital tools in turn make it possible to reduce this complexity.

Intelligent solutions require an interplay of different disciplines in the **sense of a transdisciplinarity and an interdisciplinarity**. The necessary skills can be promoted especially through problem-based and project-oriented learning. The institutes of higher education should **check whether the current structure of faculty and departmental boundaries is having an inhibitory effect** on the development of the curricula with regard to the organization of interdisciplinarity, systemic thinking, quality, flexibility and agility (↗ Thesis 1.3).

To be able to drive Digital Transformation forward in the industrial world themselves, engineering students can already at an early stage try out **entrepreneurial thinking and acting**. This is supported by links with start-up centres. Entrepreneurship, creating business plans, working with real 'use cases' as well as understanding and developing business models should be integral components of engineering education (↗ Thesis 2.1). Practical phases in companies can be supportive here. At the institutes of higher education the various **aspects of Digital Transformation can then be exchanged and reflected upon**.

Persons involved

During curriculum development, **opportunities for cooperation throughout the institute of higher education** should be explored (↗ Thesis 1.3). Interdisciplinary exchange is a possibility particularly in the case of problem-based learning projects. Especially between, but also outside of classical engineering departments can emerge forward-looking cooperation.

A **dialogue between institutes of higher education and companies, associations and unions** offers the opportunity of mutually coordinating the skills required by Digital Transformation. Here, the **responsibilities of both sides should be defined**: institutes of

higher education can teach the basic principles, deeper points of focus and learning strategies while companies, associations and unions can meet their specific requirements through training and further education opportunities. Experiences from the **integrated degree program** can be helpful here.

The process is supported by the regular **appointment of scientists from industry** in order for there to be an

adequate number of professors with business experience at the institutes of higher education.

Digital Transformation enables an improved **exchange with other educational institutions** ([↗ Thesis 3.3](#)), for example, schools, vocational schools, colleges for further education, and so on. This should be used and cared for in the spirit of individual learning pathways.

Part 3: Impulses for curriculum development

As already described in the introduction, the VDI has offered engineering education a prominent platform with its Quality Dialogues since 2007. The authors welcome the fact that the importance of engineering education has increased in recent years. This contributes to the fact that even in the years ahead graduates of German institutes of higher education will be able to enjoy an excellent starting position for their working and research lives.

The institutes of higher education are facing a variety of challenges relating to curriculum development, which have among other things already been discussed in previous Quality Dialogues but which also have been and will be addressed in a variety of other events and publications. These are mostly applicable to a broader landscape of disciplines.³

From the point of view of the authors three groups of actors are crucial to the further development of the courses of study. In addition to the institutes of higher education themselves, companies are involved as employers and politics as a party providing the framework.⁴ The focus of the following impulses is on the institutes of higher education and the economy. The challenges of politics will be tackled by the VDI together with its partners in the follow-up to the Quality Dialogue and processed separately.

Following on from the previous parts of the discussion paper, this part will also deal with the challenges for curriculum development in the engineering sciences which result from Digital Transformation. On the basis of the consequences described in the second part, impulses for reflection, revision and readjustment of the undergraduate programs are identified. This should not be understood in the sense that a large number of new modules are required but rather that the skills for Digital Transformation should be integrated into existing modules.

As already discussed, Digital Transformation succeeds in particular by linking well known technologies together as well as through transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary developments. For this reason, at the end of this discussion paper a dialogue process is proposed, which can be based on various processes, such as an organizational process, a value chain or a development process. Here, one can derive needed and desirable skills for the Digital Transformation together with the own and other departments, business

and other partners in order to introduce those in the study programs. At the same time it is also possible to determine what content has now become obsolete or can be easily updated and what content remains indispensable.

In addition, it is possible to balance with partners from the business sector which knowledge should be available and which skills and competencies should be learned in the study programs and vice versa, what during the company training and further education.

Matrix of technical skills for Digital Transformation

Not only in the incorporation of new course content but also in the evaluation and re-adjustment of current content the question always arises as to what scope, what depth of detail and what degree of abstraction is appropriate and conducive to achieving objectives. For technical skills regarding the Digital Transformation, four levels are proposed.

In the exemplary matrix (Table 1) below, a variety of possible digital techniques and methods are listed and (vertically) sorted by subject area. In addition, there is also (horizontal) sorting by the degree of abstraction. These range from the model level, via the system and technology levels, up to the application level.

In preparing development of a curriculum, a collection of all eligible course content should be made first. The sorting process that follows not only helps preserve the overview but is also supportive in discussion with partners regarding the appropriate adjustment and selection of content. Furthermore, it can provide information about which areas skills could be useful. Of course, the matrix must be customized or even created individually for each course.

The content of the matrix (Table 1) is continuously updated on the website of the 6th VDI Quality Dialogue⁵ so as to provide as many subject areas as possible for further study courses. Examples of curriculum developments are also presented on the website as possible stimuli. Beyond the sorting in the matrix, the intertwining of the teaching content can also be represented in a semantic network (Fig. 1). Here the arrows symbolize the mutual dependence of the topics. This helps when defining modules which are based on each other.

³ For example (in German): www.hrk-nexus.de/fileadmin/redaktion/hrk-nexus/07-Downloads/07-02-Publikationen/Handreichung_Anrechnung_15.12.2017_WEB.pdf

⁴ Compare Henry Etzkowitz, „The Triple Helix“ (2008)

⁵ <https://www.vdi.de/bildung/qualitaetsdialoge/6-qualitaetsdialog-ingenieurausbildung-in-der-digitalen-transformation>

Example of a matrix

	Model	System	Technology	Application
M1	Business/Management	Business/Management	Business/Management	Business/Management
	business models, investment models, value chain	ERP-, PLM-systems	digital transformation cognitive personalization knowledge management	digital eco systems/ digital system management
M2	ICT	ICT	ICT	ICT
	reference model, unifying, web x.y	big data/data analytics, smart systems, human-machine interaction	connectivity/cloud systems, internet of things, usability engineering	wearables, web x.y/ platforms
M3	Production/Logistics	Production/Logistics	Production/Logistics	Production/Logistics
	networked production process, digitized work process/smart factory, decentralization	automation, integrability, interoperability, composability, resilience, CAD/CAM-systems	robotics, working environments, production intelligence (PI)	additive and adaptive methods, maintenance, augmented/virtual reality
M4	Safety/Security	Safety/Security	Safety/Security	Safety/Security
	security/trust/privacy/safety concepts/legal basis	system safety	safe technologies, back-up technology	industrial safety systems, data protection
M5	Engineering	Engineering	Engineering	Engineering
	smart and interoperable modelling in MT	smart and flexible systems	automated mechatronic systems in production and logistics	smart lab/design thinking

Tab. 1 (Author: Prof. Schumann - For the development of the study program "Digitalization" in the context of a German-Chinese cooperation.)

Societal, personal and social skills

Not only in order to meet profound educational requirements of the course of study, in addition to the subject areas specified in the matrix the previously described societal, personal and social skills must also without fail be integrated in engineering education. The importance in connection with Digital Transformation has been described in the second part of this discussion paper and will also be a central theme of the VDI Quality Dialogue.

In addition to an overall concept for these extradisciplinary skills in the study course, for each module there should be a discussion on extradisciplinary issues. A check should be made as to how, for example, cooperation skills can be integrated into existing modules by revising the didactic concept.

Furthermore, docents should retrospectively address the interactions of earlier developments of their own discipline with society and thus regularly bring the subject of the responsibility of engineers into the course of study. On this basis, current developments can be examined with regard to their social impact. In this way, an attitude can be created in the sense of a social responsibility.

The T-shape model for a curriculum in Digital Transformation

In the competence-oriented development of modern curricula, the centre of focus is on the requirements applicable to future engineers. These are subject to a continuous process of change. In the course of Digital Transformation it is particularly important to assess what content in the light of the permanent accessibility and thus can only be addressed in the form of examples and be scaled back in the lectures. This should be done in favour of new content and options arising from digitization and also from the networking of different disciplines, and which open up new possibilities for value-added processes and finally opportunities for progress. Furthermore, content and skills need to be identified which have long-term relevance or which deliver the ability to get along with further radical changes as well as shaping those.

In this discussion paper the classic T-shape model⁶ has been supplemented with a third dimension in which the level of (possible) digitization according to the matrix can be visualized. The width of the horizontal bar symbolizes the broadness of skills including interdisciplinary competences, while the length of the vertical bar represents the depth of several of these skills – for example, through

⁶ Compare David Guest, The hunt is on for the Renaissance Man of computing, The Independent, 17.09.1991

Fig. 1: Symbolic Example of a semantic network (Author: Prof. Schumann)

modules in the advanced course. The height stands for the degree of digitization of the course content as presented above, but not in the sense of a digitized teaching. The three changes shown are

1. The adjustment of the degree of digitization of each skill,
2. The reduction of existing teaching matter (light-blue crosshatched boxes) in order to make room for new content (light-blue boxes), and finally
3. The shifting of content which was previously taught to all students (medium-blue crosshatched boxes) into the in-depth study category (medium-blue boxes).

This also has to be done individually for each course of study. The graphic should also make clear that the study's scope (footprint of the T) is not increased and that the skills for Digital Transformation should primarily be integrated into the existing content.

Dialogue process

The program committee of the VDI Quality Dialogue at the TU Berlin 2018 proposes the following dialogue process using the previous tools in order to support curriculum development. Partners from the academic and business environments should in particular be approached. With which department or level the dialogue is conducted has an effect. A discussion with the development engineers of a company may thus yield quite different insights regarding current needs than a meeting with senior management. Both viewpoints are certainly beneficial and should be internally assessed and incorporated appropriately in the curriculum.

Fig. 2: Processes in the three-dimensional T-shape model (Graphic: VDI/Gallenkaemper)

The following steps are carried out in the subsequent dialogue proposal (Fig. 3):

1. On the basis of a process (such as a project schedule of a typical company in the university environment), a skill is identified. It is further determined to what extent the necessary skill should be present (in the diagram, shown as 75%).
2. In the case of a technical skill for the Digital Transformation, the question of the required level of abstraction is clarified. This can also mean that the desire for a very specific skill is generalized or extended for the course of study. Similarly, other required skills can be identified (see also the semantic network in Fig. 1).
3. Using the information collected from the discussions with external partners, the requirements for internal curriculum development can be determined.
4. The individual components of the study program are here weighed up in relation to each other, and content, depth, scope and – where appropriate – cooperation partners defined.
5. On this basis the skills to be acquired in the course of study together with their scope can be deduced.
6. The possibility arises of discussing realistic study objectives with the external partners. These should meet the academic requirements of teaching at institutes of higher education but should also lead to graduates, which can participate in a vocational adjustment. Basic knowledge, competencies and skills are usually acquired at the institutes of higher education while specializations are taught during in-company training and advanced training.

If necessary, steps 2 to 6 are repeated once more when both sides consider a change of priorities as profitable.

Step 2 constitutes a special challenge for the dialogue. Once a very specific requirement of the graduates has been formulated in step 1, the appropriate classification and generalization is by no means a foregone conclusion. For most external discussion partners this question probably requires a changeover from an operational to a more universal perspective.

Due to the growing number of skills required and therefore increased content of teaching, there will be a stronger intertwining of the mutual dependencies of the modules. The number of these dependencies is boosted in particular by interdisciplinary modules. It is therefore all the more important to devote adequate attention to curriculum development and to intensify the dialogue within the institute. The challenges should here be approached starting from the formats being newly developed; this also means that any conflicting (internal) structures will have to be adapted. This flexibility is necessary for the adjustment of the study courses within the context of Digital Transformation.

The exchange in the last step will certainly also lead to some discussions. But precisely these are necessary not only if the institutes of higher education are to educate employable graduates but also to define appropriate objectives for the course's time framework.

It thus becomes clear as well that education for Digital Transformation does not stop with the course of study. The authors are convinced that firstly, lifelong learning is necessary for graduates to keep up with future developments, and secondly, the academic teaching must be continuously scrutinized and adapted to future developments.

Fig. 3: Dialogue process for curriculum development (Graphic: VDI/Gallenkaemper)

